

Pyramid as emitter of electromagnetic waves arising in Earth

Function of pyramid in light of electromagnetic field theory

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Abstract: *This simple geometrical structure, which the PYRAMID is, has fascinated and continues to fascinate Egyptologists, archaeologists, astronomers, mathematicians, and also mystics, and constitutes an unsolved mystery. Many theories about both the construction and purpose of these largest-in-the-world structures have been advanced. This paper presents an attempt at explaining the function of the Great Pyramid of Giza and the Pyramid of the Sun in Mexico as emitters of electromagnetic waves arising in the terrestrial medium, based mainly on the current knowledge in the fields of physics and radio astronomy.*

Key words: pyramid, cosmic radiation, electromagnetic waves, antenna gain.

1. Introduction

Pyramids were not merely the place of burial of rulers in ancient Egypt – they were also devices by means of which the souls of dead kings after their death could be transported to heaven to ensure them eternal life. It is thought that the Great Pyramid of Giza could have been designed as a facility for the magical ushering of the dead pharaoh's soul directly into the residence of gods.

There are many fanciful ideas and theories about the purpose for which the pyramids were built and the functions they were to perform after the death of a pharaoh. Most studies devoted to any other purpose of using pyramids than as monumental tombs, e.g. the view that they could have been a way of generating some form of energy, are considered to be pseudoscientific. The reason is that no sound scientific theories and proofs which would corroborate such a purpose have been produced so far.

If the pyramids in Egypt had been built only as a place of the eternal rest of pharaohs, then: *why are they all oriented according to the geographical directions N-S-E-W? why are the large pyramids in Giza so positioned along these directions that they do not obscure one another? why is the inclination of their side walls identical? why were the side walls perfectly smoothed? why is the base of the Great Pyramid made with nearly centimetre accuracy? why would ancient civilization all over the world build pyramids of the same type (the same type of structure)? why are the granite blocks exactly fitted together to constitute quite a uniform structure? and why have the pyramids no pyramidions at the top?* These are the questions to which there are no satisfactory answers yet.

Over 4000 years ago, when the pyramids were built, only natural radiation, both of cosmic origin and that escaping from the terrestrial medium, was present in the Earth's surroundings. Although very weak, it was perceptible by the then people. People at that time were more sensitive to it than now. Today, when in our immediate surroundings we are attacked by man-made artificial sources of electromagnetic radiation (networks of

tv, USW-FM radio, cellular and Wi-Fi stations, microwave ovens, etc.), our sensitivity to the very weak natural radiation has is greatly disturbed and very much dulled.

In the period when pharaohs reigned, it must have been observed that the radiation escaping from the earth was more intensive over terrain rises, knolls and hills (where it was highly dissipated and propagated chaotically in various directions) than above the flat earth. Owing to many years of observations and experience, the ancient scientists found that by properly shaping the body of a rise, the radiation could be directed, concentrated into a narrow band and radiated in a desired direction. Perhaps the aim was to exploit those natural radio waves in transporting the soul of a dead king into heaven.

As an electronic engineer, for many years dealing with the propagation of electromagnetic waves (**EM**) in different media, I focused my interests on the purely technical aspect, aiming to demonstrate that the EM energy existing in the terrestrial medium through the proper shape of a solid (e.g. a pyramid) placed above the surface of the earth can be radiated, in the form of a very narrow beam, vertically upwards into outer space. This is a novel idea based on sound, well-established and known scientific knowledge in the fields of physics and radio astronomy. As regards the question *why the rulers of that time wanted to achieve such an effect*, let Egyptologists answer it.

Still, the principal questions are: *where does the EM radiation in the terrestrial medium come from and what is its source?* There are many indications that the source of EM radiation in the terrestrial medium are **elementary particles of cosmic origin**, carrying EM information in the form of oscillations and rotations with discrete frequencies, which with enormous velocity fall into the earth. According to scientific literature, particles charged high-energy fall on the surface of the earth isotropically, with the same intensity from all directions, while the ones with lower energies fall on the surface of the earth mainly from the direction of the magnetic poles since the particles approaching the Earth from the direction of the equator are strongly deflected by the terrestrial magnetic field and do not reach the earth.

Free elementary particles with any degree of freedom, mainly electrons and protons, rushing in cosmic space in the presence of all kinds of discrete EM fields with a practically unlimited frequency spectrum, are excited by the fields. And so, e.g. a free electron, in response to a wave, oscillates backwards and forwards in the direction of the wave's electric field. Such an electron can be regarded as a kind of an oscillating electric dipole with a dipole moment. The wave's variable magnetic field does not accelerate the electron, but with the wave frequency changes its direction. The moving charged particle itself generates time-variable magnetic and electric fields. The electric field exerts a force on other charged particles in such a way that the positive charges accelerate towards the field while the negative charges accelerate in the direction opposite to the direction of the field. The magnetic field is always perpendicular to the direction of the particles' velocity, whereby it exerts a force changing only the direction of their velocity, not the velocity itself. Oscillating around the position of equilibrium, the charged particles generate EM waves and consequently, electric and magnetic fields moving through empty space with the speed of light (c). If their oscillation frequency is f , they generate an EM wave with frequency f . EM waves transport energy in space to other charged particles located even at a large distance from the original source.

Research shows that the intensity with which the free particles of cosmic radiation collide with the earth is not equal on the whole surface of the earth, the intensity at the magnetic poles being higher than near the equator. This is referred to as the latitude effect[1]. The difference between cosmic radiation intensity on the equator and at the poles is due to the Earth's magnetic field. The charged particles approaching the Earth near the two poles move almost along the direction of the magnetic force lines. They do not

encounter any force and easily reach the surface of the earth, whereby their intensity at the poles is high, whereas the charged particles which approach the equator have to travel in the direction perpendicular to the terrestrial magnetic field and are deflected in it. Only high-energy particles can reach the equator, while free particles are deflected back into outer space, whereby their intensity on the equator is minimal.

We shall now deal with the particles' EM radiation emission in the terrestrial medium.

2. EM field in terrestrial medium

Unfortunately, as to the fate of the particles falling into the earth the world literature limits itself only to the depth to which they plunge. There is nothing about the way the particles propagate in the earth, how Earth's magnetic field, which obviously exists there, affects their motion, and in what way they emit EM radiation.

Therefore, only by analogy with the behaviour of the particles in the magnetic field above the surface of the earth and with the propagation of the particles in material media one can assume that the phenomena taking place in the earth are in a way similar. One can mention here two basic EM radiation generation mechanisms: cyclotron radiation and the Cherenkov effect.

As they enter the terrestrial environment, elementary particles of cosmic origin are strongly dampened in it. The distance elementary particles travel in the earth depends on their kind, but above all on their initial energy. As I wrote earlier, elementary particles reach the Earth's surface from all directions, but the ones approaching the Earth from the direction of the magnetic poles, both the North Pole and the South Pole, reach the highest intensity. *Let us consider now how elementary particles can propagate in any arbitrary place on the terrestrial globe and along which directions they can move in the earth in order for their EM action to cause noticeable effects.*

Let us use here figure 1 showing a fragment of the Earth's surface with an arbitrarily selected observation place A, and three directions representing three areas of the incidence of elementary particles 1, 2 and 3 onto the Earth's surface at point A, most characteristic as regards the phenomena arising in the earth. Ray 1 represents all the directions of the incidence of elementary particles passing through the Earth's body, situated below a tangent to the Earth's surface at point A, except for directions deviating from the tangent by $\pm 1^\circ$. Ray 2 represents the directions of the incidence of particles passing through the Earth's atmosphere, also except for directions close to the tangent. Moreover, let us distinguish direction 3 of the incidence of rays within the angle of $\pm 1^\circ$, along straight lines close to the tangent at point A, since the particles speeding along this direction may, in certain conditions, cause noticeable EM radiation effects above the surface of the earth.

Fig. 1. Directions along which elementary particles reach point A on Earth.

First let us consider all the directions of the incidence of the particles, represented by ray *1*, passing through the whole matter of the terrestrial globe. In order to reach point *A* all these particles must cover relatively long distances *D* inside the structure of the Earth. Distance *D*, depending on deviation angle α , can be calculated from the formula

$$D = 2R\sin(\alpha), \quad (1)$$

where: *R* is the Earth's radius (equal to 6370 km) and α is the angle of ray deviation from the tangent. As it can be easily calculated, even for the small 1° deviation of the ray of incident particles the latter need to cover the distance of 222 km inside the Earth. Obviously, for larger angles of ray incidence from this direction this distance will be even greater. This means that practically no charge-bearing elementary particle of cosmic origin entering the Earth from this direction will ever reach point *A*, as it will lose its speed. Only electrically neutral neutrinos without much loss can travel such distances, causing no reaction from this medium.

The largest number of cosmic particles reach point *A* directly from outer space through the Earth's atmosphere along the directions represented in fig. 1 by rays *2*. These are mainly secondary particles arising in the Earth's atmosphere as a result of the action of the cosmic radiation of primary particles with very high energies, most often protons. As the particles of the Earth's atmosphere are bombarded by high-energy protons, various elementary particles arise, which in the form of showers hit the Earth's surface and penetrate into the earth to different depths. Muons, having properties similar to those of electrons, but 207 times heavier than the latter, are the most active particles and penetrate deepest.

We shall not consider the directions of the incidence of elementary particles onto the Earth's surface, represented by rays *2* in fig. 1, as it will turn out a little further on that even though there is an infinite number of particles falling on the Earth from this direction, their secondary effects in the earth, in the form of EM radiation above the surface of the earth are "invisible" as this radiation has no chance of escaping from inside the earth to the outside.

Instead, we shall focus our interest on the particle incidence directions denoted as *3* in fig. 1, parallel to the tangent at point *A*, as only particles entering the terrestrial environment in this way and running just under the Earth's surface below point *A* can cause the phenomena which in certain conditions can be observed above the surface of the earth. Particles running along this direction can "slide" on the surface of the earth, but they can also penetrate into its structure and fly at different depths in the terrestrial

medium under point A . Obviously, the deeper in the earth the particle runs, the longer the distance it must travel in the earth. Distance d from the place in which the particle enters the earth to the place right under point A can be calculated from the relation

$$d = \sqrt{2Rh}, \quad (2)$$

where h is the depth at which the path of the particles running in the earth under point A is located and R is the Earth's radius. It can be easily calculated that for a particle running in the earth at the depth of merely 20cm under point A , along a straight line parallel to the tangent at this point the length of the path in the earth amounts to 1.6km. Obviously, the deeper under point A the particle runs, the longer distance it must cover, and so if it moves in the earth at the depth of 0.5 m, this distance amounts to 2.5 km and if it moves at the depth of 1 m, this distance already amounts to 3.6 km.

The way EM radiation arises in the earth is similar to the Cerenkov radiation effect known in physics in the field of light waves.[2]. The passage of charged particles through a material medium with a velocity higher than the phase wave velocity is accompanied by the emission of EM waves by the particles of this medium in directions deviating from the particle travel path. A charged particle moving in a material medium with a velocity slightly lower than the speed of light (c) causes momentary polarization of the medium in the neighbourhood of the points through which it passes during motion. The medium's particles lying on the path of this particle for an instant become active coherent sources of elementary EM waves, **also the ones carried by the elementary particle.**

This can be explained in the following way. Let us assume that a charged particle moves along path AB (fig. 2) with velocity v . The partial waves emitted by the different points of path AB produce, in the direction which forms angle γ with the path of the particle, a wave with front BD . In order for the waves to amplify along this front as a result of interference, the waves must meet in a compatible phase, i.e. when the secondary wave from point A runs up to point D or C , the particle must cover the distance from point A to B .

From figure 2 follows the condition

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{u t}{v t} = \frac{u}{v} = \frac{c}{n v}, \quad (3)$$

where $u = c/n$ (n is the refractive index of the medium). Since $\cos \gamma \leq 1$, from (3) follows the relation

$$v \geq u. \quad (4)$$

Fig.2. Direction of EM radiation emitted by particle moving in material medium.

Thus, radiation is emitted only when condition (4) is satisfied, and so when the velocity (v) of the particle in a given medium is higher than the phase velocity (u) of the emitted wave.

One also comes across this phenomenon when observing the secondary radiation (in the form of air showers) of elementary particles in the earth's atmosphere, emitting EM radiation in the radio frequency range, deflected from the path of the particle by a certain angle [3].

According to the theory put forward here, charged elementary particles of cosmic origin, penetrating at the speed of light (c) into the earth's structure from the directions of both magnetic poles, generate EM radiation, i.e., around the path of travel of each particle, along radii deflected from this path by an angle equal to

$$\gamma = \arccos \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} . \quad (5)$$

Assuming that slightly moist soil whose relative permittivity amounts to 7 constitutes the outer layer of the earth's crust, the deflection angle at which radiation (5) will appear in the earth interior is equal to 67.8° .

A single isolated particle falling into the earth from, e.g., the north, emits around its path along the magnetic field lines, just under the earth's surface, EM radiation in all directions deflected from its path of travel by angle γ . Let us use figure 3, which in a top view shows a small fragment of the earth's surface and a single charged particle flying at a small depth under it in direction S . We shall focus our attention now on the EM wave propagation direction marked as V_1 in the figure since along this direction there is a chance that a coherent beam of radiation in the form of a plane wave will form. The circumstance conducive to the generation of coherent radiation in this direction is the earth's internal surface constituting the interfacial boundary between two media – the earth and the air. In the other directions, radiation has a diffuse form since, due to the vector addition of the elementary intensities of fields with random phases and various directions, the EM radiations of the particles in the particular points in the earth cancel each other out.

Fig.3. Directions of EM radiation of elementary particle in the earth.

It turns out that the EM radiation emitted in the earth by charged elementary particles can get outside, above the earth's surface, exclusively when it falls on this surface from the inside along the direction marked as V_1 in fig. 3, i.e. a direction lying along a vertical plane. This is the only direction of incidence of EM radiation originating from particles rushing in the earth, along which a refracted wave has a chance to escape above the earth's surface. If it is assumed that the particle in the earth moves with the speed of light ($\vartheta = c$) in the southern direction, then the EM radiation originating from it, in accordance with the law of refraction, after it escapes outside will continue to propagate in the southern direction, but only along the earth's surface. The radiation emitted by the particles, for other directions of its incidence on the earth's surface from the inside or for particle velocity in the earth $\vartheta < c$, **will never escape above the flat surface of the earth, it will always undergo total internal reflection.**

Total internal reflection occurs only when the permittivity of the medium in which the wave propagates is higher than that of the adjacent medium, and this is the case here.

3. Angle of inclination of pyramid's walls

If this is so, the very pertinent question arises: *what can be done in order for the EM waves carried by the particles to not only be closed inside the globe, but also to be able to be radiated from inside the earth to the outside in the form of a concentrated narrow beam?* Perhaps experts on radiation contended with a similar question also in the time of pharaohs.

Let us then in our reasoning go back five thousand years and assume the role of the person designing a pyramid with regard to its electrical aspect, i.e. someone who knew that natural EM radiation existed in the earth, what its source was and how it propagated. This person must also have known the law governing the behaviour of electromagnetic waves at the interfacial boundary between two different media and the principles of reflection and refraction of waves.

A charged particle rushing in the earth's crust with velocity close to the speed of light along a meridian in direction S generates radiation in directions deflected by angle γ from the path of its travel, including the direction which is of special interest to us

now, i.e. towards the surface of the earth. If in the place in which this radiation falls on the earth's surface from the inside the surface is flat (position a , fig.4), the radiation will undergo refraction and will travel further as l exactly along the earth's outer surface. This is so because the two velocities – that of the particle rushing in the earth and that of the EM wave above the earth's surface – are close to the speed of light. If now this fragment of the earth's surface on which the radiation from the earth's interior has fallen will be deflected from the horizontal plane, the radiation which as a result of refraction escaped outside will no longer propagate along the earth's surface but along the radius deflected from it upwards as shown in fig. 4. Of course, under the deflected surface, there must also be a medium with the same electrical properties as the earth.

Fig.4. Dependence of EM wave direction on inclination of earth's surface.

Refracted wave direction 2 and refracted wave direction 3 correspond respectively to earth surface deflection b and c , while the radiated wave direction 4 corresponds to deflection d which can be of particular interest to us. Let us now focus on the earth surface deflection at an angle close to position d . In order for the refracted wave escaping outside from the earth's interior to be re-radiated vertically upwards, the earth's surface in the place of the internal incidence of the wave must be appropriately inclined. The inclination depends on the velocity (\mathcal{G}) of the particle in the earth and on the permittivity (ϵ) of the earth under the inclined surface. The angle of refraction (α) of the wave at the inclined earth/air interface can be calculated from the relation

$$\frac{\sin \alpha}{\sin \beta} = n = \sqrt{\epsilon}, \quad (6)$$

where: β – the angle of incidence of the wave on the earth's surface from the inside.

Let figure 5, which shows a fragment of the earth's surface or the pyramid's side wall, inclined at angle φ , and the paths of the EM waves radiated by the particle in the particular phases of its travel first in the earth and then in the air, be helpful in further considerations.

In order for a narrow beam of EM radiation originating from elementary particles rushing horizontally in the earth to form above the pyramid the following two basic conditions must be satisfied:

1. The rays leaving the pyramid's side wall must be directed vertically upwards.

2. A wavefront must form in a horizontal plane above the pyramid. The time after which the EM radiation originating from the particle rushing in the earth will reach the wavefront plane will be independent of its instantaneous location.

Fig.5. Radiation of particle rushing in earth.

First condition

Assuming that after leaving the pyramid's side wall the rays, e.g., GL or KM, are vertical, we seek angle φ of this wall's inclination. From triangle DGC it is apparent that

$$\varphi = 180 - \theta - \gamma, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\theta = 90 - \beta, \quad (8)$$

substituting (8) into (7) we get

$$\varphi = 90 - \gamma + \beta = 90 + (\beta - \gamma). \quad (9)$$

Calculating the trigonometric two-sided sine function from the above expression one gets

$$\sin \varphi = \cos \beta \cos \gamma + \sin \beta \sin \gamma. \quad (10)$$

The terms of the above expression are:

$$\text{from (6)} \quad \sin \beta = \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} \quad \text{a} \quad \cos \beta = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \beta}, \quad (11)$$

$$\text{from (3)} \quad \cos \gamma = \frac{c}{n \vartheta} = \frac{1}{A \sqrt{\epsilon}} \quad \text{a} \quad \sin \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}, \quad (12)$$

where A is a ratio of particle velocity ϑ in the earth to velocity of light c in vacuum ($A = \vartheta/c$) and n is a refractive index defined as ($n = \sqrt{\epsilon}$).

Assuming that ray GL is perpendicular to the earth's surface, wall inclination angle φ and refraction angle α of the wave after it leaves the pyramid are identical ($\alpha = \varphi$) since their arms are mutually perpendicular to each other.

Substituting (11) and (12) into (10) and assuming $\alpha = \varphi$ one gets

$$\sin \varphi = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sin^2 \varphi}{\varepsilon} \frac{1}{A\sqrt{\varepsilon}}} + \frac{\sin \varphi}{\sqrt{\varepsilon}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{A^2 \varepsilon}}, \quad (13)$$

and after slight transformations pyramid side wall inclination angle φ satisfying the first condition amounts to

$$\varphi = \arcsin \frac{1}{A \sqrt{\varepsilon - 2 \sqrt{\varepsilon - \frac{1}{A^2}} + 1}}. \quad (14)$$

Let us test now what pyramid wall inclination criterion must be satisfied in order for the EM waves originating from particles rushing in the earth to form above the pyramid a plane-wave front in the horizontal plane.

Second condition

A wavefront will form when, regardless of the instantaneous location of the particle rushing in the earth, the time after the EM radiation from the particle reaches the wavefront plane is always the same.

The particle moving in the earth under the pyramid from point A towards S (fig. 5), will generate radiation in the pyramid towards vertex B . This radiation must reach point B at the same time as, after an instant, radiation from the same particle from point D reaches point L , and from point F reaches point M . Generally, the total time after which the particle's radiation will reach the wavefront plane along the path, e.g., $ADGL$, related to the location of the particle in the origin of the coordinates, amounts to

$$t = \frac{AD}{v} + \frac{DG}{u} + \frac{GL}{c}, \quad (15)$$

where v is the velocity of the particle in the earth along segment AD , u is the velocity of the EM wave in the pyramid medium along path segment DG and c is the velocity of the EM wave in the air along path segment GL , equal to the speed of light. Let us denote path segment AD as x and make the lengths of segments DG and GL also dependent on x . For easier notation let us denote segments: $AB = m$ and $AC = l$ and segment BR (equal to the height of triangle ABC) as h .

It follows from the proportion that

$$\frac{DG}{DC} = \frac{AB}{AC} = \frac{m}{l}, \quad (16)$$

where segment DC can be replaced with the expression $DC = l - x$, then

$$DG = \frac{m(l-x)}{l}. \quad (17)$$

The last of the LG segments can also be determined from the following proportion

$$\frac{AC}{AD} = \frac{BC}{BG} \quad \text{but} \quad \frac{BC}{BG} = \frac{CN}{LG} \quad \text{hence} \quad \frac{AC}{AD} = \frac{CN}{LG}, \quad (18)$$

therefore

$$LG = \frac{AD \cdot CN}{AC} = \frac{x \cdot h}{l}. \quad (19)$$

Substituting (17) and (19) into (15) and replacing AD with x one gets the formula

$$t = \frac{x}{l} \left(\frac{l}{\vartheta} + \frac{h}{c} - \frac{m}{u} \right) + \frac{m}{u}. \quad (20)$$

If it is shown that the expression in brackets is equal to zero, i.e. the sum of its two first terms is equal to the third term

$$\frac{l}{\vartheta} + \frac{h}{c} = \frac{m}{u}, \quad (21),$$

then the time after which the particle's radiation reaches the front of the waves at the pyramid height level will not depend on local coordinate x , i.e. the location of the particle. Then the formula (20) assumes the form

$$t = \frac{m}{u}, \quad (22)$$

and specifies the time needed for the EM wave to cover distance $m = AB$ from the location of the particle to the pyramid's apex at velocity u and at angle γ (fig. 5).

Let us check what the criterion for pyramid wall inclination should be this time in order for expression (21) to be satisfied.

Let us make path segments l and m conditional on height h . Hence

$$l = AR + RC = h \operatorname{ctg} \gamma + h \operatorname{ctg} \varphi, \quad (23)$$

and

$$m = \frac{h}{\sin \gamma}, \quad (24)$$

also

$$\vartheta = Ac, \quad u = c/\sqrt{\varepsilon}. \quad (25)$$

Substituting the three equations into (21) we get

$$\frac{h \operatorname{ctg} \gamma + h \operatorname{ctg} \varphi}{Ac} + \frac{h}{c} = \frac{h \sqrt{\varepsilon}}{c \sin \gamma}. \quad (26)$$

By eliminating h and c from the above equation, we get

$$\operatorname{ctg} \gamma + \operatorname{ctg} \varphi + A = \frac{A \sqrt{\varepsilon}}{\sin \gamma}, \quad (27)$$

or differently

$$\frac{\cos \gamma}{\sin \gamma} - \frac{A \sqrt{\varepsilon}}{\sin \gamma} + \operatorname{ctg} \varphi + A = 0. \quad (28)$$

From (12) we know that

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{1}{A\sqrt{\varepsilon}}, \quad \sin \gamma = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \gamma}. \quad (29)$$

Substituting (29) into (28) and calculating $\text{ctg} \varphi$ we get

$$\text{ctg} \varphi = \frac{A^2 \varepsilon - 1}{\sqrt{A^2 \varepsilon - 1}} - A = \sqrt{A^2 \varepsilon - 1} - A. \quad (30)$$

Let us use the following transformation known in trigonometric functions

$$\sin \varphi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{ctg}^2 \varphi + 1}}, \quad (31)$$

and let us substitute the second term from (30) for ctg ; then we get the same expression as (14), describing angle φ

$$\sin \varphi = \frac{1}{A \sqrt{\varepsilon - 2 \sqrt{\varepsilon - \frac{1}{A^2} + 1}}}. \quad (32)$$

It follows that the condition for the vertical radiation by the pyramid of a homogenous plane EM wave originating from elementary particles rushing in the earth at velocity \mathcal{G} will be satisfied if, for the similar permittivity ε of the earth and the pyramid assumed here, the inclination angle (φ) of the pyramid's side wall will follow the equation (32). According to literature data, the Great Pyramid of Giza is made of limestone [4] whose relative permittivity ε amounts to 7-9 while the earth's permittivity depends on its moisture content and ranges from 4 for dry earth to as much as 20 for moist earth, which means that it can happen that the two permittivities will be identical.

If the aim of the Egyptian pyramid designers was to bring the EM energy concentrated in the terrestrial medium outside and radiate it vertically upwards, it is apparent that they must have had extensive knowledge of how waves propagate in different media and of the principles of wave refraction at the interface between the media.

The mutual relations between the pyramid's wall inclination angle and the relative permittivity of the pyramid's material and the velocities of elementary particles in the earth, described by relation (32), are shown in fig. 6.

Fig.6. Relationship between pyramid side wall inclination angle φ and relative pyramid material permittivity ϵ and velocity v of elementary particles in earth.

If the pyramid is built of limestone with permittivity $\epsilon = 7$ (the yellow solid line) and the particle moves in the earth at the velocity amounting to 0.68 of the speed of light (c), the inclination of the pyramid's wall will be the same as the one adopted in the Great Pyramid of Giza [4], i.e. $51^{\circ}51'$ (the black horizontal line).

This somewhat longish mathematical argument has helped to demonstrate the very important electrical property of one of the pyramid's side walls – the south (S) wall in the considered case. Due to appropriate inclination of the wall in relation to the earth, depending on the permittivity of the pyramid's material, excellent conditions are created for the EM wave energy induced by elementary particles rushing in the earth under the pyramid to be emitted vertically upwards by the wall so that the front of a plane wave forms in a horizontal plane above the pyramid.

A similar discussion can be carried out for the pyramid's opposite wall, i.e. the north wall. Charged elementary particles of cosmic origin reach the Earth's surface also from the direction of the other pole, i.e. the South Pole, and move in the earth towards the North Pole. They are also a source of EM radiation which from the earth through the whole body of the pyramid falls on its north wall. Falling on this wall from the inside it undergoes refraction and is also radiated vertically upwards. The two radiation beams shaped by the two side walls (the north wall and the side wall) of the pyramid will form in space a very narrow single joint beam of radiation having a uniform direction and frequency.

At the time when this paper was being written, I did not manage to determine whether the pyramid's two other side walls, i.e. the east wall and the west wall, also radiate high-frequency energy. But it is possible that they do. The mechanism here can be somewhat different. The EM radiation may be influenced by particles which are deflected by the terrestrial magnetic field, enter the body of the pyramid from the east or west side and, inside the pyramid, emit EM radiation towards both the walls. It then escapes outside the pyramid also travels further vertically upwards.

4. Damping of EM wave in pyramid's body

In order to be radiated by the pyramid's side walls, the EMwaves arising in the earth must cover quite a long distance (even more than 100 m) in the pyramid's body. Obviously, they are quite strongly damped in the material of which the pyramid is made.

Since the wave damping coefficient depends on, i.a., the frequency, first let us consider the possible frequencies of this radiation. As we know, elementary particles of cosmic origin, carrying EM information in the form of oscillations and rotations with discrete frequencies, which with enormous velocity fall into the earth mainly from the direction of the two magnetic poles, are responsible for the EM radiation in the terrestrial medium. Since both above the Earth (in the Earth's atmosphere) and far away in outer space the same particles emit EM radiation which unlimitedly reaches the Earth (as it is continuously being received by terrestrial radio telescopes operating in different frequency ranges), nothing is preventing us to assume that also in the terrestrial medium these particles emit a very wide frequency spectrum. Of course, it should be noted here that both above the earth and in the earth the intensity of this EM radiation is very weak (in the order of $10^{-20} - 10^{-15}$ W). It can be received only by large antenna arrays with a high power gain (the so-called interferometers) and cannot be locally measured by simple dipole antennas or single broad-band antennas. Most generally, the coefficient of EM wave damping in a lossy material medium is expressed by the formula

$$\alpha = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu\epsilon}{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\delta}{\omega\epsilon}\right)^2} - 1}, \quad (33)$$

where:

$$\omega = 2\pi f \quad \text{and} \quad \sqrt{\mu\epsilon} = \sqrt{\mu_0\mu_r\epsilon_0\epsilon_r}, \quad (34)$$

in which: f – frequency, μ_0 and ϵ_0 – the magnetic permeability and permittivity of free space, μ_r and ϵ_r – the relative magnetic permeability and permittivity of earth, δ – the specific conductance of earth.

Substituting $c = 1/\sqrt{\mu_0\epsilon_0}$, where c is the speed of light, and $\mu_r = 1$ one gets

$$\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{2\epsilon_r}\pi f}{c} \sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\delta \cdot 18 \cdot 10^9}{f\epsilon_r}\right)^2} - 1}. \quad (35)$$

The EM wave damping coefficient (α) of the material of which the pyramid is made has been calculated assuming relative permittivity of granite $\epsilon_r = 7$ and two values of conductance: $\delta = 0.0001$ S/m for dry granite and $\delta = 0.001$ S/m for wet granite. The result of unit damping in a wide frequency range from 1 kHz to 1420 MHz is shown in fig. 7.

Fig.7. EM wave damping coefficient of material of which Great Pyramid of Giza is made versus frequency.

As one can see, the EM radiation damping coefficient of the pyramid's material increases exponentially with frequency up to about 5MHz. Above this frequency, it theoretically remains at an almost constant frequency-independent level expressed by the simple formula

$$\alpha = \frac{1635.6 \delta}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \quad [\text{dB/m}] \quad (36)$$

This applies to the frequency above which granite begins to behave as a lossy dielectric.

In the Great Pyramid of Giza the damping of a radio signal radiated in the earth at the angle of 56° (calculated from (29)) depends on the length of the distance which the wave must cover in the pyramid's body. The lower surfaces of the pyramid's walls, lying at its base, exhibit the highest radiation effectiveness since the distance which EM waves travel inside the pyramid is short and, in addition, the radiation surface area is large in this place. The greater the height, the lower the pyramid's effectiveness, the longer the distance the EM ray travels inside the pyramid and the smaller the radiation surface area. The waves heading towards the pyramid's apex experience the strongest damping, but their fraction in the pyramid's total radiation is small due to the smallest radiation surface area in this place. It is possible that this low radiation effectiveness of the highest portions of the pyramid explains why almost all the pyramids have no sharp apex (pyramidion) – it was simply not needed.

Assuming that the particle travels 20m under the surface of the ground whose relative permittivity $\epsilon = 7$, which is the same as that of the pyramid, the total damping of EM waves in the earth and in the pyramid for the frequency of 1000MHz, depending on the height at which the EM wave leaves the pyramid, will be close to the one presented in table 1.

Table1.

1	2	3
Height above earth [m]	$\delta = 0.001 \text{ S/m}$ [dB]	$\delta = 0.0001 \text{ S/m}$ [dB]
30	31	3.1
50	43.4	4.3
80	62	6.2
100	74.4	7.4
120	86.8	8.7

For the then conditions one can assume that the whole pyramid inside is very dry, devoid of moisture (calculations in column 3). This assumption can be made since when the pyramid was built its side walls were covered with cladding with a very smooth polished surface absorbing no water, which freely flowed down as on a glass surface, as opposed to the pyramid's current condition, where weathered bare rock blocks, of which the pyramid is made, have been easily saturated with water during each rainfall for hundreds of years. There is no doubt that the current damping of the EM radiation emitted by elementary particles by the pyramid's internal structure is much stronger [5].

5. Properties of pyramid as antenna

Owing to its shape, the Great Pyramid of Giza is a device radiating the energy of EM waves vertically upwards. It is a kind of directional transmitting antenna with a very narrow radiation pattern and a great power gain. The larger the antenna relative to the length of the radiated wave, the narrower its radiation pattern and the greater its power gain. In order to calculate the two parameters one may use a model in which the two radiating walls (the north wall and the south wall) can be replaced with their projections on the surface of the earth. These will be radiating elements in the form of the surfaces of two equilateral triangles with their bases equal to the side of the pyramid's base, touching each other at their vertices, with a continuous distribution of elementary EM radiation sources fed with signals with identical amplitudes and phases. This model will generate a plane wave front identical as that generated by the pyramid.

The pyramid's radiation pattern for a distance corresponding to the far-field zone has been calculated, for a few frequencies, from the formula [6] [7]

$$\frac{E}{E_{max}} = \frac{2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi a}{\lambda} \sin\alpha\right)}{a \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin\alpha\right)}, \quad (37)$$

where: a – the side of the pyramid's base, λ – the wavelength and α – the angle of deviation from the vertical. After substituting the length of the pyramid's side at its base: $a = 232 \text{ m}$ into (37), the pyramid's radiation patterns have been calculated for several frequencies and shown in the normalized form in fig. 8 for the angle of deviation from the vertical $\pm 1^\circ$. As one can see, radiation energy is concentrated in a very narrow beam. For example, for 1000 MHz the principal beam's width determined between the two minima on both sides amounts to $0.16^\circ (\pm 0.08^\circ)$.

Fig.8. Radiation pattern of Great Pyramid of Giza.

This must have been the pyramid's radiation pattern in the time when it was built, when the surfaces of its side walls were flat, smooth and shiny. The stone blocks of which the pyramid was originally made were covered with smoothed limestone and granite cladding. Remnants of such cladding survived just below the apex of the Pyramid of Khafre. The rays of sunshine reflecting from the polished tiles must have created an unusual visual effect [4]. The pyramid shone like a torch and was visible from very far away. Only on such a surface, which was the interface between two media, all the waves of natural radiation escaping from inside the pyramid **could undergo identical refraction and form a narrow single joint radiation beam directed vertically upwards**. If the Great Pyramid of Giza survived intact to the present day, the intensity of the EM signals dominating above the pyramid could be easily measured and their frequencies could be determined by means of a broadband-receiving antenna, installed, e.g., on a helicopter. Today, when the surfaces of its side walls are not smooth (due to weathering), the pyramid differs very much from the one it used to be after its construction and it is impossible to obtain a single homogenous beam of pyramid radiation. Furthermore, due to the high dampness of the pyramid's whole body, the EM radiation passing through the pyramid is damped [5], and if it escapes outside the pyramid at all, it is strongly scattered in all directions by the degenerated walls.

The other critical parameter of transmitting antennas is power gain which is the ratio of the power radiated in a given direction by an antenna with directional properties to the power radiated by a non-directional antenna and it is equal to the product of antenna efficiency η and its directive gain D , as expressed by the relation

$$G = \eta \cdot D. \quad [\text{W/W}] \quad (38)$$

There are many methods of determining antenna directive gain D but, in this case, it is most convenient to use the ones for parabolic antennas. First, one calculates the so-called effective equivalent surface of a parabolic antenna, which is interrelated with the physical surface of the antenna as follows [8]

$$A_{sk} = \nu S = \nu \frac{\pi d^2}{4}, \quad (39)$$

where ν is aperture efficiency, S – the surface of the circle and d – the diameter of the antenna. In the case of a pyramid, the radiating surface S are the surfaces of the two equilateral triangles corresponding to the pyramid's two side walls (the north wall and the south wall) in top view, touching each other at their vertices, with the total surface area described by the formula $S = a^2/2$, where a is the length of the side of the pyramid's base.

Substituting 232 m for a and assuming antenna (pyramid) aperture efficiency $\nu = 0.6$, the antenna effective area amounts to

$$A_{sk} = \nu S = 0.6 \cdot 232^2/2 = 16133.3 \text{ m}^2. \quad (40)$$

The following simple relationship between effective area and directive gain holds true

$$D = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda^2} A_{sk}. \quad [\text{W/W}] \quad (41)$$

Directive gain D of the pyramid has been calculated for several frequencies from the range 50 MHz – 1420 MHz and presented in table 2.

Table 2.

1	2	3
Frequency [MHz]	D [W/W]	D [dBi]
50	5631.6	37.5
100	22526.3	43.5
300	202736.8	53.1
500	563157.7	57.5
1000	2252631	63.5
1420	4542205	66.6

The values in column 2 mean that the power radiated by the pyramid vertically upwards is many times higher than the same power hypothetically isotropically radiated equally in all directions. The parabolic antennas used in radio astronomy for investigating cosmic EM radiation, e.g. the non-steerable Arecibo antenna with the dish diameter of 305 m, are characterized by such a directive gain.

What was the reason and purpose for concentrating by a pyramid the largest possible amount of energy into a narrow beam and radiating it from inside the earth into the outer space? The larger the pyramid, the greater its power gain as a transmitting antenna, and consequently, the greater the power density concentrated in the radiated beam. Who this energy transfer was addressed to, whether to a specific or completely unknown addressee, nobody knows.

Most evidently, the globe performs here the role of a mega demodulator which separates all kinds of radiation, in the form of EM waves, from the elementary particles, excited in outer space, falling into the terrestrial medium. This separation consists in different directions of propagation of respectively the particles in the earth and the EM waves emitted by them, as in the (known in physics and astronomy) Cherenkov effect. In astronomy in cosmic radiation investigations Cherenkov counters are used to count particles of cosmic origin reaching the earth's surface. The counters are based on the deflection of light waves. But also EM waves with other (lower) frequencies, carried by elementary particles with much lower energy, undergo the same deflection.

6. Step pyramid

The theory presented here, concerning pyramids with flat and smooth surfaces of their side walls, also applies to step pyramids, i.e. pyramids having several horizontal flat surfaces, in the form of shelves, along their side walls. The best example of such a structure is the beautiful, well-preserved Pyramid of the Sun in Mexico. Obviously, these pyramids, similarly to the ones described previously, radiate the energy generated in the earth, in the form of EM waves, vertically upwards, but the active radiation surfaces are only the inclined side walls, whereas the horizontal shelves do not take part in this radiation. The advantage of such a pyramid is that it can ensure high effectiveness of radiation through the relatively large surface of the inclined side walls at a considerably lower height. And the lower the pyramid's height, the shorter the distance the FM waves cover in the pyramid and thereby they are less damped. Owing to this, the energy radiated by such a pyramid, despite the fact that it is lower, can be comparable with the energy radiated by a flat-walled pyramid.

Let us now focus more closely on the step Pyramid of the Sun which has survived to our times in a relatively good shape.

On the side walls of the step pyramid, there are flat elements in the form of shelves whose **widths cannot be arbitrary**. They must be so matched that the particular portions of the pyramid's inclined walls, adjoining the left and right edges of each shelf, radiate energy perpendicularly upwards in a compatible phase so that a flat wave front in the form of a horizontal plane forms above the pyramid. This means that the widths of the shelves depend on the frequency and velocity of the charged elementary particles rushing in the earth under the pyramid. If the particles moved with a velocity close to the speed of light, the widths of the shelves should be equal to the total multiple of the length of the wave radiated by the pyramid: $n \cdot \lambda$ (λ – the wavelength, n – an integer). The point is that the waves, radiated by an elementary particle, reaching the shelf's edge from the inner and outer side should have the same phase. This means that the step pyramid can correctly emit radiation with only one strictly defined frequency since for any other frequency no single narrow radiation beam, in the form of a plane wave directed vertically upwards, will form above the pyramid.

Figure 9 shows one of the shelves and how it is dimensioned. Symbols D_z and D_w – stand for the distances between the shelf's outer and inner edges on the opposite sides of the pyramid. Hence shelf width $L_n = (D_z - D_w)/2$. This width of each shelf should be equal to the multiple of the wavelength, as expressed by the relation

$$L_n = n \cdot \lambda, \quad (42)$$

where n is an integer.

Fig.9. Dimensioning of one of step pyramid's shelves.

The Pyramid of the Sun in Mexico was quite precisely measured by Hugh Harleston in 1974. I found the pyramid's dimensions measured by Harleston in a Polish article [9]

(fig.1, p. 99 and tab. 1, p.93). The dimensions were corroborated by my daughter Magda who, accompanied by her husband Jacek, measured the widths of the individual shelves when, on a sightseeing tour in Mexico, they climbed to the top of the Pyramid of the Sun.

Distances D_z and D_w measured by Harleston for the particular shelves are in shown columns 2 and 3 in table 3. Column 4 contains the widths of the shelves calculated from the formula given above.

If my hypothesis, according to which the total multiple of the same wavelength is laid off along all the shelves, is true, then I should be able to find this wavelength. The point was to find a single highest number which in each of the five shelf widths in column 4 would be contained an integral number of times. I found this number to be 0.19. The expected agreement is perfectly satisfactory for the four successive shelves from the bottom (column 5). There is a small discrepancy in the case of the highest (fifth) shelf. It can be due to the not very accurate measurement of the shelf's width or to the considerable damage to the pyramid's top as a result of several hundred years of erosion.

Table 3.

1	2	3	4	5
Shelf number counting from bottom	Distance D_z [m]	Distance D_w [m]	Shelf width L_n [m]	$n * \lambda$ [m]
5	38.14	25.43	6.35	33.4* 0.19
4	68.44	57.2	5.7	30* 0.19
3	85.82	74.8	5.51	29* 0.19
2	137.2	114.4	11.4	60* 0.19
1	190.7	171.63	9.53	50.1* 0.19

The time has come now to figure out what frequency the length of 0.19m actually represents. If the wave were assumed to propagate in free space, then the frequency of 1578.95 MHz would correspond to this wavelength. Since no discrete (monochromatic) natural radiation with this frequency is known to occur in nature, one should assume that most probably this frequency is **1420MHz**– the frequency of radiation of neutral hydrogen, to which the wavelength of 0.21 m corresponds. If the pyramid actually emits radiation with this frequency, the justified question arises: why the widths of the shelves are not equal to the total multiple of the wavelength of 0.21 m, but to 0.19 m. In order to explain this, let us briefly remind ourselves that the source of the EM radiation arising in the earth are elementary particles which with an enormous velocity fly under the pyramid parallel to the earth's surface. They emit EM radiation towards the earth's surface at an angle deviating from the path of travel of the particle, expressed by formula (3). The radiated EM waves run through the pyramid's body towards its inclined side walls, get outside and, as refracted waves, proceed vertically upwards. The waves, radiated by an elementary particle, reaching the shelf's edge from the inner and outer side should have the same phase. This mechanism has been described in more detail in chapters 2 and 3. Since the particle moves in the earth, i.e. a medium denser than the air, its velocity is slightly lower than the speed of light in vacuum. Therefore, along the path corresponding to the width of, e.g., the first shelf from the bottom the particle will radiate the fiftieth wave, covering the distance of 9.5m ($50 * 0.19$) (column 5 in table 3), and not as in free space where this distance would amount to 10.5 m ($50*0.21$). It can be easily calculated that the velocity of propagation of the particles in the earth under the pyramid amounts to $\beta = 0.19/0.21 = 0.9$ of light speed c .

The Great Pyramid of Giza and the Pyramid of the Sun are comparable as regards the size of the surface area of the base: the side of the base of the former is 232m long while that of the latter is 228.8m long. Therefore, one can compare their electrical properties as transmitting antennas for radiation with the frequency of 1420MHz, which they most probably emit into space. The radiation patterns of the two pyramids in the vertical plane with direction N-S, calculated for this frequency are presented in fig. 10. As one can see, the radiation patterns of the two pyramids differ slightly. The principal beam of the radiation pattern of the Pyramid of the Sun is slightly wider and the level of some of the side lobes is much higher than that of the Great Pyramid of Giza and, as a result, the power gain of the pyramid in Mexico is lower.

Fig.10. Radiation patterns of two considered pyramids.

In order to compare the radiation effectiveness of the two pyramids for the frequency of 1420 MHz one should compare, as for transmitting antennas, their power gains. According to relation (38), this entails calculating directive gain D of the two pyramids, following from the size of the side walls' inclined surfaces emitting EM waves, and calculating efficiency coefficient η mainly dependent on the damping of the waves running inside the two pyramids. This is quite difficult to calculate, particularly if one wants to include the damping of the unit waves originating from the individual particles running under the entire pyramid, especially if the waves cover distances of different length. I leave to experts the precise calculation of the power gains of the two pyramids. Generally, without going into detailed power gain calculations, one can surmise that the radiation effectiveness of the two pyramids is similar. The effective radiation area of the inclined walls of the Pyramid of the Sun is smaller by about 34% than that of the Great Pyramid of Giza but, since the former pyramid is twice lower, the intensity of the signal radiated by it is higher due to the fact that the signal is less damped by the pyramid's body.

It is apparent that the designers of the Pyramid of the Sun achieved a similar, or even better, result by designing a lower pyramid which was easier to build and required much less material. A major limitation of the Pyramid of the Sun was that it emitted radiation solely with the frequency of 1420 MHz, as opposed to the Great Pyramid of Giza which could similarly effectively emit each kind of radiation, with any frequency, arising in the earth.

7. Conclusions

Recapitulating, let us try to figure out the purpose of sending the same EM wave radiation with the frequency of 1420 MHz, brought by vibrating particles to the Earth, back into outer space in a specific direction. Maybe the EM radiation delivered to the Earth by charged particles of cosmic origin was modulated with some information which was to be transmitted to somebody in outer space. Or perhaps the radiation directed towards the heavens was supposed, after the death of a pharaoh (placed in the pyramid), to transport his soul from the Earth to heaven. The pyramid could have been used in the period prior to the expected death of a person, not necessarily a pharaoh, and when this person died and his/her soul left him/her, rising to heaven, the body was carried out of the pyramid and buried in another place. The funeral ceremonies took place inside the Great Pyramid, they were meant to convey the souls of Egyptians to the other world, and the pyramid itself served not only one pharaoh, but many generations of Egyptians. No burial has been found to have taken place in any of the Egyptian pyramids, and there are about 70 of them. All the pharaohs, and especially the greatest and most powerful rulers, such as Ramesses II and Thutmose III, were buried in the famous Valley of the Kings.

The pyramids could have served medicinal purposes. The sick were placed inside the pyramid in rooms specially built for this purpose, situated in specific places with specific properties, were subjected to natural radiation with the frequency of 1420 MHz, which was most probably known to the contemporaries and used for health purposes.

Or perhaps the internal properties of the pyramids were helpful in mummifications of people, and also animals, commonly performed in those times. Corpses could be stored in the pyramid's rooms for some time and undergo the drying process and then be embalmed with no fear that they would decompose.

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